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THE COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ADJECTIVES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the usage and draws an analogy to adjectives by the levels of morphology in two different languages. Adjectives are seen in particularly different ways by Eastern and Western linguists, and even within setting to set side by side in order to show differences and likenesses. The past is over, but present you can seize, and make it for you in the immediate future. So, there are some similar and different features of adjectives which we have tried to demonstrate in English and Uzbek languages.

Keywords: English and Uzbek languages.

In both English and Uzbek, adjectives are essential for enhancing descriptions and giving conversations more nuance¹. The way adjectives indicate comparison degrees and transmit ideas like superiority, equality, or inferiority is an interesting feature of adjectives. In order to shed light on the various forms and usage of adjectives in the English and Uzbek languages, we will examine the similarities and contrasts between the two languages in this article.

English adjective degree: An essential part of English grammar, adjective degree allows speakers and writers to characterize nouns with a range of comparison or intensity levels. Adjectives give details about a noun's qualities, which can be articulated in three different ways: superlative, comparative, and positive.

1. In a positive degree: The most fundamental type of adjective is the positive degree, which is used to characterize a noun without making a comparison. - It's employed to convey a quality's presence without drawing comparisons to other things. Positive-degree adjectives include big, tiny, tall, happy, sad, and beautiful.
2. Comparative Degree: Two objects or two sets of characteristics are compared using the comparative degree. Comparative degree adjectives frequently have a "-er" at the end or come before "more." - Adjectives with one or two syllables

¹ .Eissenberg J. Comparative Studies in Uzbek Syntax: The Case of the Q-Particle. – Amsterdam: John Benjamins Publishing Company, 1993. – 240 p.

often take the "-er" suffix when forming the comparative degree, whereas longer adjectives take "more." - More, less, taller, happier, sadder, and more attractive are examples of comparison adjectives.

3. Superlative Degree: The superlative degree is employed when comparing three or more objects or to describe the highest level of a quality. - Adjectives in the superlative degree usually finish in "-est" or are preceded by "most." - When generating the superlative degree, adjectives with one or two syllables typically take the "-est" suffix, whereas lengthier adjectives take "most." - Adjectives in the superlative degree include biggest, smallest, tallest, happiest, saddest, and most beautiful.

Adjectives in Uzbek can be inflected to indicate three levels of comparison²: positive, comparative, and superlative. 1. Positive degree: This is the adjective's base form, which is used to characterize a noun without drawing comparisons.

For instance: Yaxshi (good). katta (large) ko'p (many). 2. Comparative degree: This adjective is used to compare two items or individuals. In Uzbek, the comparative degree is constructed by adding the suffix "roq" to the positive form of an adjective. For example: yaxshiroq (better). kattaroq (larger) ko'proq (more) 3. Superlative degree: This adjective is employed when comparing three or more things or individuals. In Uzbek, the superlative degree is constructed by adding the suffix "chi" to the positive of an adjective. For example: - eng yaxshi (the best) - eng katta (the biggest) - eng ko'p (the most) It's important to note that some adjectives in Uzbek have irregular forms in the comparative and superlative degrees, so it's best to consult a dictionary or reference guide for specific examples. Overall, understanding and using the three degrees of comparison in Uzbek adjectives can help you effectively describe and compare different qualities or characteristics in the language.

Both English and Uzbek utilize adjectives to describe nouns and convey degrees of comparison, although their methods differ slightly.

Similarities is Basic Function: Adjectives in both languages modify nouns to provide descriptive information. Degrees of Comparison: Both languages express degrees of comparison, but English uses a formal system with suffixes while Uzbek relies on adverbs and comparison word³.

² Ruzmetov J. Uzbek-English Dictionary. – Tashkent: Goslitizdat, 1979. – 830 p.

³ Kortmann B., Schneider E.W. A Handbook of Varieties of English: Morphology and Syntax. – Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter, 2004. – 1056 p.

Differences in Formal System: English employs a formal system for forming comparative and superlative degrees, while Uzbek lacks such a system and relies more on word order and adverbs. Suffixes: English often uses suffixes (-er/-est) or the words "more" and "most" to form degrees, whereas Uzbek uses adverbs and comparison words more frequently. Structure: English adjectives typically precede the noun they modify, whereas Uzbek allows for more flexibility in word order.

In conclusion, in English, adjective degree is formally structured into positive, comparative, and superlative forms, often achieved through suffixes or the use of "more" and "most." Adjectives generally precede the noun they modify, and there are strict rules governing their usage and placement.

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